

THE MARRIAGE OF FORENSIC MUSIC AND FORENSIC DANCE FOR TOURIST DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA

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Abstract

This paper discusses the marriage of forensic music and forensic dance for tourist development in Africa. The writer examined the styles of native musical performances and the native dances of the people of a place. The work also identified the musical forms inherent in the musical contents. Historical and descriptive methods were employed for the study. It was discovered that musical compositions and performances do communicate tremendously. Dances also communicate greatly. The communication realities in music as well as dance were based on understanding of the cultural patterns of any African people(s) at that particular time. It is recommended that the various African music genres as well as the various dance genres should be carefully utilised and/or harnessed music and dance ensembles as well as the music with dance ensembles to depict the cultural nuances of the people(s).

Keywords: Forensic Music, Forensic Dance , Tourist Development
